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Representation of modelling and simulation driven research workflows as cognitive processes for ontology-based knowledge and data management in the engineering sciences

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Abstract. This position paper argues that FAIR research data management and semantically interoperable knowledge representation in computational engineering are best advanced by a system of semantic artefacts and tools that are based on a formal model of cognitive processes and the main outcome of cognitive processes: Knowledge claims. Such an approach emphasizes what modelling and simulation have in common with other practices and processes, in scientific research and beyond, and will therefore be particularly amenable to ontology alignment and the integration of data from heterogeneous sources within data infrastructures.

Keywords: Interoperability · digitalization · simulation workflows.

1 Introduction

Simulation platforms rely on a variety of approaches for representing modelling and simulation workflows, which need to be aligned with each other to obtain interoperable and reusable provenance metadata and to exchange workflow descriptions and capability statements between multiple digital infrastructures. These workflow descriptions, which are here collectively referred to as process models, are often very technical, operating at a low level [9, 18, 26]; consequently, they can be highly domain-specific (*e.g.*, restricted to materials modelling) or tailored to the language of a particular community of users, or both, as is the case with the Review of Materials Modelling (RoMM) [4] and MODA (*i.e.*, “model data” tables), the semi-formal workflow description CEN workshop agreement [6] that was endorsed by the European Materials Modelling Council¹ (EMMC ASBL) until 2021, when the CEN workshop agreement expired. To satisfy interoperability requirements, top-level ontologies [29, 30, 39] – such as the BFO [2], DOLCE [5, 25], and the EMMO [8, 12, 37] – are increasingly considered as a component that can support mapping divergent semantic spaces to each other. Moreover, a number of graphical notations are in use for simulation workflows; at a high level, this includes the Object Management Group’s DMN and BPMN [1, 20, 21, 28, 38]. At the domain level, there are MODA graphs [4, 6] and,

¹ URL: <https://emmc.eu/>

recently, the powerful “physical topology” notation proposed by Preisig [34, 36] in the context of his process modelling suite ProMo [34, 35].

For workflow documentations based on the expired MODA metadata standard, an extensive corpus of examples is available [4] due to the consistent use of MODA within a line of development from Horizon 2020 [11]. MODA graphs have been improved, yielding the logical data transfer (LDT) graph notation [16], and MODA itself has been developed into an ontology, the Ontology for Simulation, Modelling, and Optimization (OSMO) [16, 17], which is one of the Virtual Materials Marketplace² (VIMMP) domain ontologies³ [13]. However, it will be necessary to go beyond MODA, since its limitations have now become clear to the community; these limitations include the rather idiosyncratic arrangement of data items in MODA, making it very hard to align [22] with other related semantic artefacts such as the EMMO top-level ontology⁴ that is widely used within the very same community. Moreover, MODA is by design narrowly limited to a static set of “physics equations,” listed in RoMM [4], by which it cannot exploit the many features that research workflows in computational engineering share with research workflows in general, or even the foundational features that are shared with cognitive processes and cognition at a high level of abstraction.

Addressing these gaps, the present work argues that a formal model of cognitive processes and their outcomes, expressed as knowledge claims, can support knowledge representation and semantic interoperability for FAIR research data management in materials modelling. It is explored how the Physicalistic Interpretation of Modelling and Simulation/Interoperability Infrastructure⁵ (PIMS-II) mid-level ontology [14, 22] should be further developed for this purpose.

2 Formal model of cognitive processes

Following Peirce’s approach to semiotics [24, 31, 32], an elementary cognitive step is a process which is conceptualized as a *triad* and starts from the previously established *representation relation* between a sign s (*i.e.*, a representamen) and an object o (*i.e.*, the referent of the representamen); the cognitive step adds a third element to the sign and the object, by which a new representation relation is created. In the case of a semiosis σ , the third element is the interpretant s' , *i.e.*, a new representamen, such that the triadic cognition can be denoted by

$$\sigma : s - o - s' [\kappa]; \tag{1}$$

there, for instance, σ can be a simulation of a system or process o , where s is all or a relevant part of the simulation input (*e.g.*, a model of o), and s' is all or a relevant part of the simulation output (*e.g.*, a property of o), such that o is the

² URL: <https://vimmp.eu/>

³ URL: <https://gitlab.com/vimmp-semantic/vimmp-ontologies>

⁴ Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (formerly called the “European Materials and Modelling Ontology”); URL: <https://github.com/emmo-repo/>

⁵ URL: <http://www.molmod.info/semantics/pims-ii.ttl>

Fig. 1. Fragment of the cognitive step taxonomy (conceptual hierarchy) from PIMS-II; arrows denote conceptual subsumption.

common referent of both s and s' . Above, κ is the preceding cognitive step from which the representation relation between s and o is carried over.

Symmetrically complementing this scheme, in a **Metonymization** μ , the sign is assigned a new referent o' , yielding a triad

$$\mu : o - s - o' [\kappa], \quad (2)$$

such that a subsequent cognitive step can build on the representation relation between s and o' . For instance, s could be a molecular model of methane, initially thought of as representing an intermolecular interaction (such that o would be a pair of methane molecules), that we are about to use as a simulation input to compute thermodynamic properties of a macroscopic amount of methane o' .

3 Mereosemiotics

Mereosemiotics, the interaction between participation in a cognitive process and spatiotemporal parthood and contact [14, 15], is implemented in PIMS-II on the basis of a three-way case distinction between three branches of the cognitive step taxonomy: Perception, interpretation, and metonymization, *cf.* Fig. 1.

In a **pims-ii:Perception**, a subclass of **pims-ii:Semiosis**, all the three representational elements from the Peircean triad, s (sign), o (object), and s' (interpretant), need to participate physically, which is characterized by spatiotemporal overlap of the representational elements with the cognitive step.

In a **pims-ii:Interpretation**, another subclass of **pims-ii:Semiosis**, s and s' need to be present, whereas this is not required for the object; *e.g.*, we can simulate an explosion without the need for an actual explosion to occur at the same time and location of the computational environment where the simulation is run.

In a **pims-ii:Metonymization**, the sign s needs to participate physically, whereas the old referent o and the new referent o' need not. For instance, predicting the

pressure in a reactor o (with composition and temperature gradients) using an equation of state s can be metonymized to applying s to a homogeneous control volume o' at equilibrium; neither the reactor nor the control volume have to be in physical contact with the computer that evaluates the equation of state.

Eventually, outcomes of the research workflow, namely, *knowledge claims* deduced and possibly published by the researcher(s), are obtained in the role of a Peircean representamen. These are the elements that require the most careful documentation: While for some purposes (*e.g.*, reproducibility studies [7, 33, 40, 43]) the workflow as such will need to be reused, it is always mainly the research outcome, *e.g.*, as a FAIR-compliant digital object [45], not mainly the research process, that FAIR research data management aims to make reusable and machine-actionable [19, 27, 44]. It is helpful if workflow management systems are designed such that the computational workflows self-annotate in a FAIR way [16, 18, 45]; however, it is not only helpful, but absolutely necessary for FAIR compliance that the outcomes, *i.e.*, the knowledge claims, are annotated using community-recognized metadata standards. Reinforcing this perspective, Durán and Jongsma [10] make the theoretical argument that transparency of all the algorithms and the workflow “falls short of offering the right epistemic reasons for trusting the outcome”; empirically, Schmidt *et al.* [42] observe that increased transparency does not improve trust in the outcome (rather, the opposite) even where the outcome as such should warrant a high level of trust.

4 Conclusion

PIMS-II based documentations of research workflows *as cognitive processes*, summarized above, have two main advantages: First, they highlight features that modelling and simulation have in common with other research practices, experimental work in particular, whereas RoMM and MODA concentrate on creating a catalogue of specifics that do not generalize. Therefore, this approach will support the integration of experimental and simulation based data [3], *e.g.*, within disciplinary research data infrastructures [41]. Second, metadata documented via PIMS-II are straightforward to map to the EMMO, supporting interoperability with a multitude of EMMO-aligned domain ontologies and digital infrastructures from Horizon 2020 and, in the future, from Horizon Europe [23]; contrast this with the massive obstacles encountered when using MODA, requiring elaborate mechanisms, *e.g.*, based on graph transformation [22].

Moreover, it was proposed here that the central object to be made FAIR is the research outcome, not the research workflow. While the documentation of the workflow (*i.e.*, the cognitive process) is important, the documentation of the obtained knowledge claims (*i.e.*, Peircean signs as such) deserves at least as much attention; there, it is possible to build on EMMO efforts, with modifications as regards the possibility for the same data item – the same sign – to be present in multiple spacetime regions, for example due to copying, without creating mereological contradictions [15]. In the PIMS-II mid-level ontology, semiotic collective objects are introduced in order to represent such scenarios consistently [14]. Since

MODA has expired and a new CEN agreement will be needed anyway, it may be beneficial to use Preisig's physical topologies, the most promising candidate that is sufficiently advanced to replace MODA, in combination with PIMS-II and other EMMO compliant semantic artefacts and tools.

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